

PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS ON THE UPBRINGING OF A BOY IN
THE INTERPRETATION OF WESTERN PHILOSOPHERS

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Abstract. This article examines the philosophical views of Western philosophers on the upbringing of boys based on contextual analysis. With the development of society, the forms and methods used in the theory and practice of upbringing have gradually changed, and we can observe that various views, opinions, and theoretical approaches related to the problems arising as a result of upbringing and their solution have improved in connection with socio-historical development. The concepts of upbringing methodology, its place and role in human life, and the problems of its importance in practical life have found expression in the works of such Western philosophers as Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, Jean-Jacques Rousseau, Claude Adrien Helvétius, Denis Diderot, and Immanuel Kant.

Key words: *upbringing, family, society, boy, upbringing methodology, state, Renaissance*

Western thinkers have always sought human identity, which has remained in the distant past from the mysterious and legendary East, simple human relationships, especially sincerity and love, devoid of false and hypocritical compliments, any selfishness and material interests. They were convinced that the issue of upbringing was embodied in the very essence of these relationships.

Scientific knowledge about the theory of upbringing in the ancient Eastern peoples began to be mastered by the Greeks and Romans by the 1st millennium BC. The development of the polis in Greece in the 9th-8th centuries BC, and the great Greek colonization in the 8th-6th centuries BC, allowed them to get to know

other peoples around the Mediterranean and the Black Sea and exchange products with each other. On the other hand, during this period, the process of the formation of centralized states in countries such as ancient Egypt, Babylon, Assyria, Syria, and Phoenicia was completed. By this time, “a decisive step was taken to understand the world through the human mind, from a religious-mythical understanding of it”[1]. It is noted that in the states that emerged during this period, the issue of education rose to the level of state policy, was considered a state task, and direct involvement in education was transferred to the state. For example, the Spartans tried to “raise children to be strong, physically healthy, resilient, and trained warriors.” Their boys lived at home until the age of 7, then were placed in a state-organized educational institution called “agella,” where they were educated and raised until they reached the age of 18. The heads of these institutions were prestigious and well-known people appointed by the state, and they were called “pedonomists” and supervised all educational work. In particular, special attention was paid to the upbringing of adolescents, who were trained with various exercises to be physically healthy, taught to endure cold, hunger and thirst, and to endure pain. In the Spartan education system, after boys reached the age of 18-20, they were transferred to a special group of “ephebes” (ephebes were adolescents who had reached puberty in ancient Greece) and underwent military service”[2]. Thus, in the process of upbringing in Sparta, mental, moral, aesthetic and physical education were carried out in a harmonious manner.

With the development of society, the forms and methods used in the theory and practice of education have gradually changed, and we can observe that various views, opinions, and theoretical approaches related to the problems arising as a result of education and their solution have improved in connection with socio-historical development. This "changes in social-historical, socio-scientific, and cultural foundations have led to changes in the foundations of educational methodology and the formation of a new educational methodology." The concepts

of educational methodology, its place and role in human life, and the problems of its importance in practical life were expressed in the works of such Western philosophers as Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, Jean-Jacques Rousseau, Claude Adrien Helvétius, Denis Diderot, and Immanuel Kant.

Ye.Ye.Fyodorova writes, “There are three specific levels of Socratic dialogue. The first level is the conversation itself or in the form of dialogue, the second level is in the form of strategic discourse, which characterizes the form of dialogue in the process of development. The third level is called metadiscourse, which concerns the rules for conducting dialogue.[3] “Plato, on the other hand, emphasizes that “education should be organized by the state and serve the interests of the ruling groups, and recommends that boys be educated from the age of 3 to 6 under the guidance of state-appointed tutors. From the age of 7 to 12, he recommends that they study in state schools and teach them reading, writing, arithmetic, music, and singing. It emphasizes that boys aged 12-16 should study at the "Palestra" school, which teaches physical exercises, until the age of 18 in schools teaching secular sciences, and until the age of 18-20 in "Efeb" schools, where they should receive military training. After graduating from the "Efeb" school, capable and talented young men should undergo a third stage of higher education, which teaches philosophy.

Aristotle, paying attention to such a systematic process as “family-state-personal virtue-will harmony” in the upbringing of a boy, developed methodological aspects of the theory of upbringing in his time. In general, the views of the philosophers of antiquity on upbringing had a strong influence on the views of Western European philosophers.

In general, despite the fact that the views of the ancient philosophers Socrates, Plato, and Aristotle were put forward based on the interests of the society of that time, in their views, the possibility of achieving happiness by raising a boy as a morally mature person is of paramount importance.

One of the distinctive features of medieval Western civilization was corporatism. During this period, the French philosopher-enlightenment Jean-Jacques Rousseau criticized scholastic methods of education and upbringing in his work "Emile, or On Education" (1762), which was devoted to the problems of pedagogy. He argued that the first task of the school is to educate a true man and citizen. He was a supporter of independent thinking in children. [4]

Another French Enlightenment philosopher, Claude Adrien Helves, unlike other philosophers of his time, viewed the abilities of boys as a product of upbringing, believing that "all people have the same abilities and therefore respond equally to the beneficial effects of education. The theory that Helves adopted from Locke and made the basis of his philosophy was that education determines human success." [5] Jean H. Bloch notes that "Helvésian views had a strong influence on the formation of J.J. Rousseau's pedagogy, and also provided him with the opportunity to express his controversial views. [6]

Another famous German philosopher who put forward his philosophical views on the upbringing of a boy is Immanuel Kant. His ideas on the theory of upbringing serve as a methodological basis for the development of modern views on upbringing. According to researcher R.K. Khaitmetov, "I. Kant understood education to mean the formation of knowledge and skills and considered it to refer to natural upbringing, which includes the development of physical strength and mental abilities and the formation of discipline. "Education, on the other hand, is concerned with the formation of morals and ethics, and is different from school education or training (the acquisition of skills) and pragmatic education (the attainment of intelligence), and is concerned with practical education." [7]

The main theme of Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel's philosophy of education is Bildung, which is translated as "education", but it is more consistent with the concepts of "formation", "development", "culture". With its help, Hegel reveals the process of self-development of the mind or Spirit embodied in culture

and history. In his opinion, "The main task of education should be to deepen the soul through consciousness and commonality and help the learner overcome his natural simplicity and wildness.

The above contextual analysis allows us to put forward the following conclusions:

Theories on the methodology of education, the problems of its place and role in human life, and its significance in practical life are an interesting and relevant topic that has been studied with great interest by Western philosophers from ancient times to the present day as the main philosophical problem in the focus of attention;

In the school of ethics created by the ancient Greek thinker Socrates, he focused on the formation of general qualities in boys, as well as on specific qualities, such as courage, wisdom, moderation, justice, and others. Plato was a supporter of "education being organized by the state and adapting it to the interests of the ruling groups." Aristotle argued that "in order for a perfect person to be a perfect citizen, the state must also be perfect," and that "although the highest goal is to achieve truth through observation and intellectual intuition, human nature is imperfect," and that because of this imperfection, "life feels a need for a number of blessings and virtues";

While one of the Western Renaissance philosophers, J.J. Rousseau, put forward his idea of "free education", Gelves, unlike other philosophers of his time, viewed the abilities of boys as a product of upbringing and saw "education as the key to human success";

D. Diderot showed that "every person has individual development opportunities and characteristics by nature, but their manifestation depends on the influence of society and upbringing," and indicated the need for an institutional approach to the issue of upbringing, while I. Kant paid special attention to the issue of moral duty in the upbringing of boys and approached upbringing from a

structural-functional perspective. It was highlighted that the main theme of Hegel's philosophy of upbringing is Bildung, and although this term is translated as "education", it is more consistent with the concepts of "formation," "development," and "culture," and that the formation of the human "I" is of paramount importance based on his philosophy.

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